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XY-69 Liposome Substrate Preparation and Assay Optimization for

Monitoring PLC γ 2 Enzymatic Activity In Vitro

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Introduction

1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2, PLCG2) is an enzyme that converts PIP2 (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate, PtdIns(4,5)P2, PI(4,5)P2) into IP3 (1D-myo-inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate) and diacylglycerol (DAG). PLC γ 2 is mainly expressed in immune cells and microglia, but only sparsely expressed in other brain cells such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.[1] A rare coding variant in PLC γ 2, Pro522Arg (P522R) was identified from an Alzheimer's disease genome-wide association study (GWAS)[2] and replicated in various populations.[3,4,5] This mutation was found to confer a protective effect where patients who carried this P522R mutation exhibited a slower rate of cognitive decline than patients who did not.[6] While the exact mechanism of this protective effect of the P522R PLC γ 2 mutant is not fully understood, this mutation does induce a slight increase in enzymatic activity.[1] Therefore, pharmacological intervention that increases the wild-type PLCG2's activity may provide a therapeutic strategy to lessen the cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease patients.

At the time of writing, published literature described only two molecules that activate phospholipase C (PLC) enzymes in vitro, U73122 (1-(6-((17 β -3-methoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-yl)amino)hexyl)-1H-

pyrrole-2,5-dione) [7] and m-3M3FBS (2,4,6-trimethyl-N-(meta-3-trifluoromethyl-phenyl)-benzenesulfonamide) [8]. U73122 has been shown to activate PLC β and PLC γ family members in vitro [7], but it was originally identified as an inhibitor of PLCs.[9] In fact, U73122 was extensively used as the prototypical inhibitor of PLC enzymes in cell culture.[10,11,12,13,14] However, more recently U73122 has also been shown to effect numerous other cellular proteins including phospholipase D [15], 5-lipoxygenase [16], calcium channels [17], potassium channels [18], telomerase [19], histamine H1 receptor [20], and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase.[21] This complete lack of specificity is not surprising as the maleimide in U73122 can react with the thiol present in cysteine residues. Therefore, it is highly likely that U73122 non-specifically reacts with exposed cysteines on numerous proteins within a cell. This lack of specificity and high reactivity make U73122 a poor option to base a medicinal chemistry campaign with the goal of developing selective PLC γ 2 activators.

U73122

m-3M3FBS

m-3M3FBS was originally identified from a screen of compounds that enhanced superoxide-generating activity in human neutrophils [8]. This activity was proposed to be caused by the direct activation of PLCs.[8] Supporting this proposition, several labs have shown that the downstream signaling effect of PLC activation – intracellular calcium release, was observed in various cell types treated with m-3M3FBS.[22,23,24,25,26] However, the potency and specificity of PLC activation of m-3M3FBS has been called into question as there are reports that intracellular calcium release occurs before any PLC activity is detected[27] and that m-3M3FBS effects the inward and outward flow of ions in a PLC-independent manner possibly through the direct inhibition of delayed rectifier potassium channels.[28] Additionally, m-3M3FBS has been shown to be cytotoxic in some cell lines.[23,24,25] Currently, it is unclear if m-3M3FBS exerts its activity primarily through PLC activation and if it does, whether a derivative could be identified that is selective for PLC γ 2.

As no selective small molecule activators of PLC γ 2 are currently known, there is a clear need to identify such an activator to determine whether the pharmacological activation of PLC γ 2 is a viable therapeutic strategy to treat Alzheimer's disease. Fortunately, there are enzymatic assays that have already been developed that are amenable for high-throughput screening (HTS).[29,30] These assays were primarily developed to identify inhibitors of PLC enzymes,[31] but these assays and substrates can be readily modified to screen for PLC γ 2 activators. These assays can be broadly classified into two groups. The first utilizes a water soluble substrate epitomized by WH-15 that measures the catalytic activity of PLC enzymes in solution,[29] while the second uses a hydrophobic substrate such as XY-69 that imbeds in a micelle or liposome to measure the activity of PLC enzymes at a surface interface that better mimics the natural membrane-bound substrate PIP₂ [30].

In this resource document, we detail the protocol of using the previously reported XY-69 substrate [30] to monitor the activity of PLC γ 2 on liposomes. This substrate and generalized protocol should be amenable to other phospholipase C enzymes as well.

Preparation of Liposomal XY-69

Liposomal XY-69 was prepared by modifying previously reported methodologies [31,32,33] for optimal monitoring of PLC γ 2 activity. The protocol to create these XY-69-containing liposomes is detailed below:

1. 16 μ L of XY-69 (200 μ M) in water was dried in a glass culture tube under a gentle stream of N_2 for 30 min.
2. 79 μ L of phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP2, 1 mg/mL) in chloroform/methanol/water (20:9:1) and 30.5 μ L 1-stearoyl-2-arachidonoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphatidylethanolamine (lipid PE, 10 mg/mL) in methanol were added to the glass tube containing the dried XY-69.
3. The mixture was dried to completion under a gentle stream of N_2 for 60 min
4. The lipid film was re-dissolved in 110 μ L of a 1:1 $CHCl_3$:MeOH solution.
5. The solution was dried under a gentle stream of N_2 for 90 min to give a lipid film on the bottom of the tube.
6. The film was then subjected to high vacuum for at least 90 min to remove all trace of solvents.
7. 1 mL of 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4) was added to the dried film.
8. The material was pulsed using a 3 mm sonicator probe tip at a depth of \sim 5 mm into the fluid with three cycles of pulse, 5 sec ON (20% output) and 10 seconds OFF.
9. The lipid mixture then was processed by six cycles of freeze-thaw by submerging the tube for 90 seconds in a $-78^\circ C$ acetone and dry ice bath followed by thawing for 3.5 min in a $34^\circ C$ water bath.
10. The resulting lipid vesicles (1 mL, lipid PE: 408 μ M, PIP2: 72 μ M and XY-69: 3.2 μ M) were incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes.
11. A 1/5th equivalent volume (200 μ l) of 6X Lipid Vehicle Assay Buffer (LVAB, 120 mM HEPES, 420 mM KCl, 4.5 mM $CaCl_2$, 18 mM EGTA, pH 7.4) containing 20 mM DTT and 0.18 mg/ml BSA was added to the 1 mL lipid vesicle solution, and the resulting 1.2 mL solution was vortexed for 20 sec.
12. The resulting lipid vesicle solution (LVS, lipid PE: 340 μ M, PIP2: 60 μ M, XY-69: 2.7 μ M, 20 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 0.75 mM $CaCl_2$, 3 mM EGTA, pH 7.4) with BSA (0.03 mg/ml) was utilized for PLC γ 2 enzymatic assay.

PLC γ 2 Enzymatic Assay with Liposomal XY-69

PLC γ 2 wild-type (WT) and the PLC γ 2 Alzheimer's protective mutant (P522R) were expressed and purified by the Mesecar lab at Purdue University. Expression and purification conditions can be found in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562203>. A general protocol for the determination of enzymatic activity of these PLC γ 2 proteins is described below:

1. 1 μ M of PLC γ 2 WT or P522R mutant (20 mM HEPES, 150 NaCl, 5 %v/v glycerol, 1 mM DTT) was diluted with 1 X LVAB (20 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 0.75 mM $CaCl_2$, 3 mM EGTA, pH 7.4) containing 0.03 mg/ml of BSA (acid free) to yield a final protein concentration of 8 nM.
2. 5 μ L of PLC γ 2 WT or the P522R mutant were plated in the wells of a black 384-well microtiter plate
3. 15 μ L of LVS (described above) were added to the wells containing PLC γ 2 WT or the P522R mutant (final concentration: 2 nM, lipid PE: 255 μ M, PIP2: 45 μ M and XY-69: 2 μ M, $CaCl_2$: 0.75 mM, BSA: 0.03 mg/ml)
4. The plate was placed on a plate reader and its fluorescence intensity (ex: 485 nm; em: 520

nm) was recorded every 2 min for 90 min.

Validation of PLC γ 2 Enzymatic Assay with Liposomal XY-69 Using PLC γ 2 Mutant (P522R) and the PLC γ 2 inhibitor, ATP

To further validate the ability of our modified XY-69 liposomal assay procedure to monitor the enzymatic activity of PLC γ 2, differing concentrations of PLC γ 2, the activating PLC γ 2 mutant P522R, and the PLC γ 2 inhibitor ATP (adenosine triphosphate) were utilized as activation and inhibition controls. The enzymatic reactions of PLC γ 2 WT and its mutant (P522R) were performed as described above. Wells that contained ATP were made using the following protocol:

1. 1 μ L of ATP (100 mM in Tris buffer) or water was added to the wells of a black 384-well plate.
2. 5 μ L of PLC γ 2 WT and 15 μ L of LVS were added to the wells containing PLC γ 2 WT or P522R mutant (final concentration: 1.9 or 3.8 nM protein, lipid PE: 255 μ M, PIP₂: 45 μ M, XY-69: 2 μ M, CaCl₂: 0.75 mM, BSA : 0.03 mg/mL, ATP: 4.8 mM)
3. Fluorescence intensity was monitored (every 2 min for 90 min) as described above.

Figure 1. Validation of PLC γ 2 Enzymatic Assay with Liposomal XY-69

PLC γ 2 showed enzymatic reactivity in a dose-dependent manner (PLC γ 2 1.9 and 3.8 nM). The activating PLC γ 2 mutant P522R showed a greatly increased level of activity when compared with the wild type PLC γ 2. ATP inhibited PLC γ 2 enzymatic activity. These results suggest that this liposomal assay with XY-69 is feasible to assess PLC γ 2 activity.

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